

PREDICTIVE ROLE OF NEGATIVE LIFE EVENTS IN DEPRESSION: SEROTONIN, NOREPINEPHRINE, AND PHARMACOTHERAPY INTEGRATION

AN ANALYTICAL PAPER

Author: P. Rupondo

Africa International University, Department of Psychology, Karen
Published 15 December 2025, Copyright © 2025 Rupondo P.,
DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17934779>

KeyWords

Negative life events, depression, serotonin, norepinephrine, pharmacotherapy, predictive factors

ABSTRACT

Depressive disorders are a global mental health concern with significant implications for individual well-being and societal functioning. This paper explores the relationship between negative life events and the development of depressive disorders, emphasizing the role of neurobiological factors, specifically serotonin and norepinephrine, in the manifestation of these conditions. Drawing from recent research, the paper examines the interplay of psychological, biological, and social determinants in shaping depressive symptoms. It highlights the biological underpinnings of depression, focusing on neurotransmitter imbalances and hormonal dysregulations, including serotonin and norepinephrine, and their contribution to mood regulation. Social determinants, such as socio-economic status, social support, and life events, are also discussed as influential factors in depressive outcomes. The paper underscores the importance of integrating pharmacological and psychosocial interventions to address the complex nature of depressive disorders. Through this framework, the paper aims to provide an understanding of depressive disorders, offering insight into potential intervention strategies for improving mental health outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global landscape of health is significantly shaped by the burden imposed by mental health disorders, the most prevalent being depressive disorders. This paper will explore the dynamics that link negative life events to the predisposition and development of depressive disorders. The focus is specifically directed towards unravelling neurobiological complexities involving serotonin and norepinephrine. The paper will navigate through the physiological dimensions of depressive disorders and attempt to shed light on how these neurochemical processes intersect with psychosocial stressors. The integration of pharmacotherapy will be undertaken, providing an insight into the complexities of the relationship between biological and environmental factors influencing the manifestation of depressive disorders. The paper will show the multi-layered nature of depressive disorders thus presenting a nuanced understanding and potential intervention strategies.

1.1. Depressive Disorders and their Prevalence

Depressive disorders are a common mental disorder with the terminology often used interchangeably with the term depression. According to the WHO¹, (2023) statistics, depressive disorders affect approximately 5% of the adult population worldwide, with 1 in every 3 women and 1 in every 5 men affected. These statistics show that women are more likely to get depressive disorders more than men, (WHO, 2023, Albert, 2015). According to Gbadamosi, Henneh, Aluko et al, (2022), the depressive disorder prevalence in Sub-Saharan countries within the WHO Africa region, show a rate of 4.1% which is notably lower than Americas, 4,8% and Europe at 4,9% respectively. Africa alone has approximately 30 million people with depression (9%) with a notable figure of 7 million in Nigeria alone and South Africa, (9,8%) of the population.

Many people suffer from these illnesses throughout their lifetime. The illnesses are, not the same as regular mood shifts and feelings involving everyday functioning. They involve a depressed mood or loss of pleasure in activities over extended periods of time. The illnesses include major depressive disorder (MDD²) which is ranked the most prevalent and disabling mental disorder worldwide (Gutiérrez-Rojas, Porrás-Segovia & Dunne, et al, 2020). The Global Burden of Disease, injury, and risk Factors study, (GBD³) conducted in 2019, illustrating that MDD was ranked in the top 25 of the leading causes of the global health burden, (COVID-19 Mental Disorders Collaborators*, 2021).

Africa contributes 10% to the global burden of mental disorders, with 5.4% being depression

¹ WHO - World Health Organisation

² MDD - Major Depressive Disorder

³ GBD - Global Burden of Disease, injury and risk Factors study

and 3.2% being anxiety, (Gbadamosi, et al, 2022). The study showed that the burden of depressive disorder remained higher throughout the entire lifespan of both males and females in diverse regions across the world. Other depressive disorders include bipolar disorder, dysthymic disorder, and cyclothymic disorder, (APA, 2017, WHO, 2023). Depressive disorders are more likely to affect persons who have experienced traumatic events and challenges situations in their lives, such as severe losses or abuse. The illnesses pause a debilitating impact on the psychological, social and physiological elements of the affected persons and their community, (who, 2023, Gutie´rrez-Rojas, 2020).

1.2. Determinants of Depressive Disorders

Depression is a complex condition that can be influenced by a wide range of psychological, social as well as biological factors, Monteiro, Pereira, & Relvas, (2015) Coryell, (2023). Remes, Mendes & Templeton, (2021) conducted a study to review 470 relevant literatures on depressive disorder from 2017 to 2020. The objective of the study was to synthesise literature focusing on biological, social, and psychological determinants of the illness. The study found that a diverse range of risks and protective factors were interconnected across all determinants. The findings emphasised the connectedness of causation that influenced depressive outcomes. This study therefore confirms the risks and complex relationship of factors that influences the development of depressive disorders. The writer will briefly discuss *psychological, biological and social determinants* of depressive disorders.

1.2.1. Psychological Determinants of depressive disorders

Psychological factors include several factors such as, heightened sensitivity, neuroticism, ruminations, maladaptive coping, and dysregulated emotional functions, (Remes, et al 2021, Monterio et al, 2015, Coryell, 2023). Zineldin, (2021) conducted a study on 141 participants to uncover the psychological and neurological factors that influence depressive disorders. The findings of this study showed an interconnection between the two factors. The findings emphasized that a reduced quality of life and depression are related as they impact thinking, emotions, feelings, and actions, (Monteiro, et al, 2015, Coryell, 2023). Psychological factors are significant in the development and regulation of depressive symptoms.

1.2.2. Biological determinants of depressive disorders

The biological determinants of depression encompass many factors, such as physical health conditions, genetic predisposition, the microbiome, inflammatory processes, stress response system and cognitive functions. This paper will focus on hormones, and neural circuitry determinants show the complex interactions between biological and mental health processes.

1.2.3.1 *Hormones and neurotransmitters: Serotonin (5-HT) and Norepinephrine (NE)*

Depression includes a complex relationship of hormones and neurotransmitters in the brain, including serotonin, norepinephrine, and cortisol. An imbalance in these chemical messengers contribute to depressive symptoms development. Serotonin and norepinephrine are principal neurotransmitters in the CNS.

Serotonin (5-HT) is a neurotransmitter, a chemical messenger in the brain that has a significant role in physiological functions and behaviour, (Cowen, 2015). The association between serotonin and depression is complicated and not fully realized. There is evidence of irregularities in serotonin processes in depressed patients, however it is unclear if these abnormalities directly cause depression, (Moncrieff, Cooper, Stockmann, & Timimi, 2022, Cowen, 2015). Research in the field of neuropsychology continues. Serotonin neurotransmitter is associated with mood regulation, sleep, appetite control and sexual functions and plays a major role in feelings and the happiness of a person, (Zeldin, 2021). The neurotransmitter is synthesised from the amino acids tryptophan in the brain, and these are mainly found in the gastrointestinal tract (peripheral tissues) as well as the nervous system of the body. It is primarily found in the central nervous system (CNS). The primary source of serotonin is the collection of nuclei in the brain stem (raphe nuclei) which project regions across the brain and influence mood, appetite, and sleep cycles, (Cowen 2015, Zeldin, 2021). According to Cowen, (2015), Moncrieff et al, (2022), the disturbance in the activity of serotonin (5-HT) pathway on emotional processing and automatic emotional response is viewed as a cause in the pathophysiology of depressive symptoms. Increased serotonin activity also leads to improved subjective mood and visa-versa, (Cowen, 2015). Serotonin is also important in the recovery from the illness. Jauhar, Cowen, & Browning (2023), stated that low levels of plasma tryptophan an antecedent of serotonin have been discovered in persons with more sever forms of depression.

Norepinephrine (NE) is both a hormone and a neurotransmitter, that belongs to the catecholamine family. It is primarily found in the CNS and is released by neurons in brain cell nuclei (locus coeruleus) which project widely in the brain and affect arousal, stress and responses. In the peripheral tissues, the norepinephrine acts as a neurotransmitter in sympathetic nerve affecting organs as well as tissues. The hormone neurotransmitter is also released into the blood stream through the adrenal glands during stress responses of the body. Norepinephrine is responsible for executive functioning, regulating cognition, motivation and intellect and plays an important role in the body stress response, alertness, fight, or flight responses, as a neurotransmitter. The (NE) hormone is released into the blood stream and influences organ functioning. Norepinephrine is synthesised by dopamine located in the nerve cells of adrenal glands. Maletic, Eramo, and Gwin, et al, (2017) state that norepinephrine (NE) is plays a

significant role in the pathophysiology of major depressive disorder (MDD) and schizophrenia. The elements controlled by NE are significant in daily functioning, e.g., social functioning. When social dysfunction affects the quality of life of those affected by the illness, (Maletic et al, 2017).

The Hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) dysregulation is closely connected with the NE and 5-HT imbalances, (Jauhar, et al, 2023). The HPA axis functions closely to the LC–NE system. The NE and the cortisol (CRH) are the major regulators of the HPA axis system and regulate stimulation in the brain regions, peripheral organs and physiological downstream of the central release system. The HPA is the core response system that stimulates behavioural arousal and the increase of cardiovascular activity as well as the interference with the routine neurovegetative functioning, (Bao, A.-M., & Swaab, D. F. (2018)). The HPA is the key element of body stress response which includes the hypothalamus, pituitary glands and adrenal glands. Elevated cortisol levels in the HPA dysregulation may negatively affect the synthesis, release and re-uptake of the neurotransmitters including norepinephrine and serotonin. When the HPA is dysregulated, there is an imbalance in the neural circuits that govern mood and functioning, and NE and 5-HT are vulnerable to these activities. Dysregulation of NE signalling may affect the HPA axis functioning, adding to the development of mood disorders, (Maletic et al, 2017).

The study by Zineldin, (2021) on 141 participants illustrated earlier in this paper also focused on neurobiological elements of depressive outcomes. The study found that external control (EC) that is, mood controlled by others was strongly linked to depression through neural circuits. Neurotransmitters and hormones found in the central nervous system and peripheral tissues such as serotonin and norepinephrine are important components of the neural circuit that regulates mood and emotional wellbeing.

Finally, *cognition processes and functions (metacognition)* such as attention and memory as well as all executive functions have been confirmed by studies to be linked to the depressive mood development and outcomes, (Remes et al, 2021). Low cognitive functions, vulnerability or deficit and decline as well as the regression of dendritic branches, neuroplasticity impairment, hippocampal atrophy and neurogenesis aspects have been associated with depressive mood development. The above shows the connectedness of neurobiological elements with depressive mood disorders and understanding these sheds light the development of appropriate measurements.

1.2.3 Social determinants of depressive disorders

Social determinants of depressive symptoms are elements found within the environment of a person, (Phiri et al, 2022, Remes et al, 2021). These social elements can be categorised as social

structural social capital, socio demographics, social support and cohesion, occupational elements, environmental activities, significant life events, ethnicity, and status (migrants), security, crime and abuse and socio-economic status. All these aspects have been found to have a link with the development and outcomes of depressive, (Dagnino, et al, 2020), for example, socio economic status may influence one's access to quality health care services which affects their wellbeing. Furthermore, lack of education impacts the ability to access information and make informed health decisions (Dagnino, et al, 2020). Elements such as unemployment and instability cause a lack of security affecting self-esteem and a sense of purpose. When one does not have adequate or stable social relationships such as friends and family, then one does not have a good sense of belonging or necessary protective factors that are essential for emotional, financial, or general support and may increase depressive mood symptoms and outcome determinants, (Dagnino, et al, 2020, Remes, et al, 2021).

In summary, the complexity of depressive disorders is shaped by the interaction of psychological, biological, and social determinants. These factors intertwine as determinants of depressive disorders symptomatology and outcomes. The interlinks highlighted by Remes, et al, (2021) and Zineldin, (2021) underscore the need for a comprehensive approach to interventions for depressive disorders. The next section will focus on negative life events as predators of depressive disorders.

2 NEGATIVE LIFE EVENTS, DEPRESSION AND NEUROBIOLOGICAL COMPONENTS

Negative life events are usually identified as significant predictors of depressive disorders. These events include personal losses, relationship difficulties to financial crisis or traumatic events. They contribute to the development of depressive symptoms and outcomes of the illness, (Phiri et al, 2022, Remes et al, 2021). Negative life events can create substantial stress and challenges an individual's coping mechanisms. The emotional toll of such events may become overwhelming for one to handle. Negative life events form the social determinants discussed in the former.

2.1 Negative life events trigger the Body's Stress response system,

The hypothalamic pituitary adrenal thus triggering the release of hormones that regulate mood. A prolonged exposure to these hormones for example serotonin affects the brain structures associated to mood regulation, and norepinephrine; executive functioning thus contributing to the development of depressive disorders, (Jauhar et al, 2023, Moncrieft, 2022, Bao et al, 2018, Maletic et al, 2017, Cowen, 2015). For example, losing a source income can cause a significant financial strain. Remes et al, (2021), state that trauma and negative life events are associated with depressive symptom development. The authors highlighted the life course

mental health studies and how they reflect significant life experiences as precursors of shaping mental health trajectory, (Phillips, Carroll, & Der, 2015).

2.1.1 *Chronic Adversity*

Chronic adversity refers to persistent and lengthy exposure to difficult life situations over extended period. These challenges can have a significant impact on a person's well-being. Examples of chronic adversity include. Chronic adversities may include family dysfunctions and chronic illnesses. Negative life events such as traumatic events, and chronic adversity have a significant impact on brain function and structure, resulting in the possible development of major depressive disorders, (MDD) and posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Negative life events such as dealing with a *chronic illness* e.g., cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and other chronic illnesses are linked to an increased risk of depressive disorders. A study conducted in Turkey by Phiri, Aydın, and Yıldız et al, (2022) on the risk factors of chronic illnesses found that prevalence of depression amongst affected persons was high with a significant association with chronic illness such as cardiovascular disease, (Dagnino, Ugarte and Morales et al, 2020). Managing the physical symptoms, quality of lifestyle shifts, and potential worries may contribute to increased risk of depressive symptoms.

2.1.2 *Causal Relationships*

According to Remes, et al, (2021), there is a bidirectional relationship between the negative life events and depressive symptoms (*causal relationship*). For example, a person facing a job loss and financial strain may experience feelings of hopelessness leading to depression. The difficult circumstances act as the cause (independent variable) and influencing the development of depression as the effect (dependent variable). While individuals' responses vary from person to person as well as support systems, negative life events play a crucial role in shaping depressive outcomes. A research study in the late 1990s by Kendler, Karkowski, & Prescott, (1999) on 15 classes of stressful life events and major depression onset over a period of a year on female twins for threat and dependency found that stressful life events have a significant causal relationship with MDD onset.

2.1.3 *Cumulative Burdens*

Another element of negative life events in the *cumulative burden* which refers to the combined impact resulting from the accumulation of various factors. These may include life stressors and challenges build up over time and play a role in the increase of the risk for depressive symptoms. Ongoing and increasing stressful life events for example heavy workload at work, marital problems at home, personal chronic illness, and financial instability, all for one person to

carry may lead to depressive symptoms. Gutie´rrez-Rojas, Porras-Segovia, and Dunne, et al, (2020) stated that socioeconomic status may be associated with major depressive disorders. Cumulative burden makes one susceptible to persistence depressive symptoms.

2.1.4 Vulnerability and Resilience

Negative life events and their impact on depressive symptoms may be influenced by *vulnerability and resilience* factors. The concept of vulnerability and resilience are rooted. It is all about the individual's ability to response to the environment or adversities. Low resilience results in vulnerability to psychiatric illness while high resilience results in coping with the adversity, (Elisei, Sciarra, Verdolini, & Anastasi, 2013). Psychological resilience is the ability to cope in the face of adversity. The neural circuits of resilience responsible for adaptive functioning dysregulation may result in abnormalities in the pathways that increase depressive symptom occurrences, (Wu, Cohen, & Kim et al, 2013). Biological factors such as the HPA axis, play a significant role in the development of resilience responses to trauma and adversity, (Wu, et al, 2013). Gutie´rrez-Rojas, et al, (2020) stated that personality can affect coping strategies and the capacity to overcome adversity.

A study by Norton, (2017), on the relationship between depression and resilience in survivors of childhood trauma on variable such resilience and gender, resilience and income, and resilience and trauma. The study found that resilience and depression have a correlation such that as one increases, the other decreases and vice-versa. Some people struggle with resilience and become more susceptible to depressive disorders, (Phillips, et al, 2015). Two people lose their jobs. Character Blue has a good support system, can cope effectively and motivated about life and has hope. While character Red has no robust support system and lacks coping skills with a more negative outlook on things. Therefore, Character Red has low resilience and is more vulnerable to acquiring depressive disorders.

2.1.5 Metacognitive Processes

Negative life events are intertwined with *neurobiological factors* such as genetic predispositions which have a significant impact on the duration of the symptoms. *Metacognition processes* such as thought patterns contribute to the increase of depressive symptoms. Chen, Zhang, & Yang, et al (2023) conducted a study on 703 college learners and discovered that *ruminations* mediate the relationship between social issues and depressive symptoms. They emphasised the role of ruminations over negative life events in the development of depressive disorders. One loses sleep and constantly thinks about their job loss. They develop into maladaptive coping mechanisms influencing alcohol use for example. Understanding the connection between negative life events and depressive symptoms is crucial in the determination. Testament and

management of depressive disorders.

3 THE ROLE OF PHARMACOTHERAPY

Pharmacotherapy: that is the of medications, is significant in the treatment of depressive symptoms. The medications for depressive disorders known as antidepressants, aim to ease the symptoms by influencing the levels of neurotransmitters in the brain, such as serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine., (Maletic et al, 2017). Norepinephrine play an important role in pharmacological treatment of depressive disorders, (Juahuar, et al 2023)

3.1 Different Classes of Antidepressants

There are various classes of antidepressants in the treatment used in the treatment of depressive disorders. These include selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, (SSRIs), the serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors, (SNRIs), monoamine oxidase inhibitors (MAOIs) and tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), (Juahuar, et al 2023, Meltic et al, 2017). Each type has specific functions in the treatment of depressive symptoms. *Antidepressants* like the SSRIs and SNRIs help to increase the availability of serotonin and norepinephrine in the synaptic cleft therefore leading to the increase and decrease of depressive disorder symptoms such as mood. When serotonin is released into the synapses, it is then reabsorbed by the presynaptic neurons through the reuptake. The SSRIs and the SNRIs function by binding to and blocking the serotonin transporter reuptake therefore allowing the serotonin to remain within the synapse for a longer period. An increased concentration in the synapse assist in the enhancement of the neurotransmitter leading to the reduction of depressive symptoms. Tricyclic antidepressants help to block the reuptake of both serotonin and norepinephrine leasing to the concertation of the neurotransmitter in the synapse.

The MAOIs inhibit the activity of the monoamine oxidase that primarily breaks down serotonin and norepinephrine as well as dopamine. Inhibiting this enzyme thus increases the neurotransmitter availability in the synapse. Chronic use of antidepressants alters the adaptative changes of the neurotransmitters and hormones. The use of anti-depressants influences neuroplasticity and influence the alteration of neuronal structures and functions. *Antipsychotics* are commonly used for the treatment of schizophrenia however the atypical antipsychotics such as clozapine are used to regulate the norepinephrine signalling in the prefrontal cortex and other brain regions. *Other medications* such as alpha-adrenergic receptor agonistics have also been applied in the treatment of major depressive disorders. Glucocorticoid receptor antagonist impacts the HPA and have been tested as potential treatment for MDD.

3.2 Correcting Neurotransmitter Imbalances

Antidepressants function by correcting imbalances in neurotransmitters, which are chemicals that transmitting signals between the nerve cells. These treatments enhance the availability of neurotransmitters in the brain and help the regulation of mood. Cowen (2015) indicated that studies on the SSRIs commonly used as antidepressants have shown that repeated administration leads to molecular changes in the hippocampus cell proliferation of an animals. They studies show an enhancement of expression of neuroplasticity proteins and a positive shift in the brain's appraisal function of emotional information, mediated through the serotonergic innervation to the limbic system, (Juahuar, 2023). Wu et al, (2013) states that neurotransmitter imbalance is corrected by the altering the gene that regulates the hypothalamus pituitary adrenal axis (HPA). This plays an important role in the shaping of resilience in persons affected by depressive symptoms.

Individuals respond differently to pharmacotherapy. It takes many weeks for a therapeutic effect to be visible and at times various medications may be tried for each person until the effective one is found. Most clients may require both psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy in order to fully benefit from treatment protocols that combat both biological and psychological elements. Those affected by chronic illnesses may require long term pharmacotherapy management with remission intervals and relapse prevention strategies. Pharmacotherapy has side effects for some clients and these should be managed to ensure that they do not exacerbate the symptoms. Pharmacotherapy can be very effective depressive symptoms reduction and improving overall functioning and wellbeing. Comprehensive treatment approach that includes therapy and quality of lifestyle changes are necessary.

4 CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, negative life events have revealed their predictive role in the development of depressive disorders, through interconnected pathways that influence neurotransmitters, serotonin, and norepinephrine. Adverse life experiences can lead to dysregulation in the neural circuits which is associated with mood regulation and executive functioning thus impacting the synthesis, release, and reuptake of these crucial neurotransmitters. The imbalance in the serotonin and norepinephrine is a significant contributor to the manifestation of depressive symptoms.

Addressing these imbalances, pharmacotherapy using antidepressants, plays a significant role. The medications like SSRIs and SNRIs target the dysregulated neurotransmitters to restore balance by modifying the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine. The integrated approach, considering both the psychosocial impact of negative life events and the neurobiological elements underlying depressive symptoms, provides a comprehensive outline for understanding and treating depressive disorders. The recognition of the complex relationship between life

experiences and neural circuitry, mental healthcare professionals can design interventions that include both psychosocial support and pharmacotherapy to assist in the improvement of depressive symptom outcomes those affected.

REFERENCES

- Albert, P. R. (2015). Why is depression more prevalent in women? *Journal of Psychiatry and Neuroscience*, 40(4), 219-221. <https://doi.org/10.1503/jpn.150205>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2022). Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th ed., text rev.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425787>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2022). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th ed., text rev.)*. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425787>
- Bao, A.-M., & Swaab, D. F. (2018). The human hypothalamus in mood disorders: The HPA axis in the center. *Neurobiology of Stress*, 9, Article 100180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibror.2018.11.008>
- Chen, G., Zhang, G., Yang, Y., Zhang, J., & Hu, Y. (2023). Relationship Between Negative Life Events and Depressive Symptoms for Chinese College Students: The Mediating Role of Rumination and Moderating Role of Perceived Social Support and Psychological Capital. *Psychology Research and Behaviour Management*, 16, 271-282. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S360149>
- Coryell, W. (2023). Depressive Disorders. *MSD Manual*. Retrieved from <https://www.msmanuals.com/professional/psychiatric-disorders/mood-disorders/medications-for-treatment-of-depression>
- COVID-19 Mental Disorders Collaborators*. (2021). Global prevalence and burden of depressive and anxiety disorders in 204 countries and territories in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. *The Lancet*, 398, 1700-1712. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02143-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02143-7)
- Cowen, P. J. (2015). Serotonin and depression: Pathophysiological mechanism or marketing myth? *World Psychiatry*, 14(2), 161-163.
- Dagnino P, Ugarte MJ, Morales F, González S, Saralegui D and Ehrental JC (2020) Risk Factors for Adult Depression: Adverse Childhood Experiences and Personality Functioning. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 11:594698. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.594698
- Elisei, S., Sciarra, T., Verdolini, N., & Anastasi, S. (2013). Resilience and depressive disorders. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 25(Suppl. 2), 263-267.
- Gbadamosi, I. T., Henneh, I. T., Aluko, O. M., Yawson, E. O., Fokoua, A. R., Koomson, A., Torbi, J., Olorunnado, S. E., Lewu, F. S., Yusha'u, Y., Keji-Taofik, S. T., Biney, R. P., & Tagoe, T. A. (2022). Depression in Sub-Saharan Africa. *IBRO Neuroscience Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibneur.2022.03.005>
- Gutiérrez-Rojas, L., Porrás-Segovia, A., Dunne, H., Andrade-González, N., & Cervilla, J. A. (2020). Prevalence and correlates of major depressive disorder: a systematic review. *Brazilian Journal of Psychiatry*, 42(6), 657-672. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2020-0650>
- Hasler G., (2010). Pathophysiology of depression: do we have any solid evidence of interest to clinicians? *World Psychiatry*. 2010 Oct;9(3):155-61. doi:10.1002/j.2051-5545.2010.tb00298.x.
- Jauhar, S., Cowen, P. J., & Browning, M. (2023). Fifty years on: Serotonin and depression. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 37(3), 237-241. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02698811231161813>
- Kendler, K. S., Karkowski, L. M., & Prescott, C. A. (1999). Causal Relationship Between Stressful Life Events and the

- Onset of Major Depression. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, 156(6), 837. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.156.6.837>
- Maletic V, Eramo A, Gwin K, Offord S, J, and Duffy RA (2017) The Role of Norepinephrine and Its α -Adrenergic Receptors in the Pathophysiology and Treatment of Major Depressive Disorder and Schizophrenia: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 8:42. doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2017.00042
- Moncrieff, J., Cooper, R. E., Stockmann, T., & Timimi, S. (2022). The serotonin theory of depression: A systematic umbrella review of the evidence. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02698811231161813>
- Monteiro, S., Pereira, A., & Relvas, R. (2015). Risk Factors for Depressive Symptomatology Among Higher Education Students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 191, 2025–2030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.467>
- Phiri YVA, Aydın K, Yıldız NG, Motsa MPS, Nkoka O, Aydın HZ and Chao HJ (2022) Individual-level determinants of depressive symptoms and associated diseases history in Turkish persons aged 15 years and older: A population-based study. *Front. Psychiatry* 13:983817. doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2022.983817
- Phillips, A. C., Carroll, D., & Der, G. (2015). Negative life events and symptoms of depression and anxiety: stress causation and/or stress generation. *Anxiety, Stress & Coping*, 28(4), 357-371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10615806.2015.1005078>
- Remes, O., Mendes, J. F., & Templeton, P. (2021). Biological, Psychological, and Social Determinants of Depression: A Review of Recent Literature. *Brain Sciences*, 11(12), 1633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11121633>
- Rahman, O., Tariq, P., & Mian, J. F. (2021). Risk and protective factors for depression: A comprehensive review of the literature. *Brain Sciences*, 11(12), 1633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11121633>
- Norton, Marquis A. (2017). Exploring the Relationship Between Depression and Resilience in Survivors of Childhood Trauma. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Dissertation, Counselling & Human Services, *Old Dominion University*, DOI: 10.25777/fbfg-1w65
- Qubekile Y, Paruk S, Paruk F. Prevalence of depressive symptoms and quality of life among patients with diabetes mellitus with and without HIV infection: A South African study. *South African Journal of Psychiatry*. 2022;28(0), a1762. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajpsy.2022.28i0.1762>
- World Health Organization. (2023). *Depression*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/depression>
- Wu, G., Feder, A., Cohen, H., Kim, J. J., Calderon, S., Charney, D. S., & Mathé, A. A. (2013). Understanding resilience. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, 7, Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2013.00010>
- Zineldin, M. (2021). Neurological and Psychological Determinants of Depression, Anxiety, and Life Quality. *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*. DOI: 10.4103/ijpvm.IJPVM_237_192021